

FACTORS INFLUENCING GENERATION Z CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOR IN ONLINE SHOPPING IN JAYAPURA CITY PAPUA PROVINCE

ANITA ERARI ¹ and OSCAR OSWALD O. WAMBRAUW ²

^{1,2} Faculty of Economics and Business, Cenderawasih University, Jayapura, Papua-Indonesia.
Email: ¹erarianita29@gmail.com, ²wambrauwooscar79@gmail.com

Abstract

Excessive consumption, without using a priority scale or prioritizing desires and pleasures over needs, occurs suddenly or without planning. This is known as consumer behavior. By conducting research on native Papuan students at State Universities in Jayapura City, this research aims to study the influence of financial literacy, digital payments and financial technology on the behavior of Generation Z consumers in Jayapura City in shopping online. This research uses primary data from respondents who meet the research criteria. Non-probability and total sampling were used. This research is quantitative and uses multiple linear regression analysis to analyze the data. From the results of this research, Generation z, Indigenous Papuan students at Jayapura City State Universities are expected not to get used to the YOLO (You Only Live Once) and FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) mindset so as not to fall into excessive consumerist behavior which can endanger welfare. finances in the future. Likewise, Generation z, Papuan students at Jayapura City State Universities are also expected to be wiser by having self-control in using digital payment financial technology (fintech digital payment) so that they are not easily tempted by the ease of transactions that would otherwise be carried out. controlled can encourage someone to behave consumptive.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Fintech Digital Payment, Finance, Consumer Behavior, Generation Z, Papua Province.

INTRODUCTION

Consumptive behavior is often an issue in each individual's shopping behavior patterns. Consumptive behavior is a pattern of individual consumption behavior that makes purchases not based on needs but rather desires caused by trends that are followed or the visual attractiveness of a product (Sustiyo, 2020). Kurniawan (2017) defines consumptive behavior as excessive behavior, without using a priority scale or prioritizing desires and pleasures over needs in consuming something. The definition of consumer behavior is also defined as a type of consumption behavior that is carried out suddenly or without planning, arises from irrational attitudes (Effendi et al., 2021), and only prioritizes desires alone (Fattah et al., 2018). Based on the results of research conducted by Kurniawan (2017), the factors that influence student consumer behavior are: 1) following developments in trends (40%), 2) wanting to look different from other people (30%), 3) a sense of pride in their appearance excessive self (15%), and 4) wanting to attract the attention of others (15%). Apart from that, several other factors/variables that can influence individual consumptive behavior according to several other studies are: lifestyle, sales promotions from e-commerce platforms, and hedonic shopping motivation (Venia et al., 2021); conformity and celebrity endorsement (Effendi et al., 2021); financial literacy, self-control, use of social media Instagram, individual modernity, and pocket money (Ayuningtyas & Irawan, 2021; Sustiyo, 2020; Silalahi, 2020; Susanti & Rikah, 2020;

Kumalasari & Soesilo, 2019; Fattah et al., 2018), demographics and income (Purwanto, 2019) as well as the use of digital payment financial technology (fintech) products in the form of digital wallets or e-wallets (Nur'Aini et al., 2021; Kumala & Mutia, 2020; Dewi et al., 2021; and Kusuma, 2020) and mobile banking; (Dewi et al., 2021; Mufirdah, 2020 and Syifa, 2019). The consumer behavior of generation z is also often associated with the character of generation z who adheres to the YOLO (You Only Live Once) and FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) mindset, thus making this generation begin to adopt trend developments as their lifestyle. This phenomenon is also illustrated in the results of a pre-survey research on Generation Z Lifestyle, Department of Management, UPN Veteran Jakarta, which shows that trend developments also influence 66% of students in carrying out the purchasing process (Ramadanti et al., 2021).

The flow of globalization has brought humans towards a new civilization called the "digital era" where technology, information and communication are developing very rapidly. The digital era is well known for the phenomenon of digital transformation which makes people faster, easier and more efficient in carrying out their activities and work. This technological progress also has an impact on various industrial sectors in Indonesia, including the economic sector which has begun to transform from a conventional economy to a digital economy. The development of digitalization in the Indonesian economic sector is marked by the presence of e-commerce and financial technology (fintech). E-commerce is also defined as an interaction between two parties in carrying out sales and purchase transactions for products or services via the internet network (CommerceNet in Indrajit (2002)). Several reasons why Indonesian consumers choose online shopping are shown in the following graph of Sirelo survey results (2021):

Figure 1 1: Reasons for Indonesian Consumers Choosing Online Shopping (Online Shopping)

Generation Z of native Papuan students at Jayapura City State University do not yet have self-control in using digital payment financial technology (fintech digital payment), are not yet wise in managing their personal income and expenses. In relation to the phenomenon of generation Z's consumer behavior in online shopping, e-wallet and mobile banking as financial technology (fintech) digital payment products exist as stand-alone payment applications and have features that are integrated with other applications. With the development of fintech digital payment innovation, now online bill payments, balance transfers to individuals, as well as online shopping payment transactions can use QRIS (Quick Response Code Indonesian Standard) issued by Bank Indonesia on the 74th anniversary of the country.

Dewi et al. (2021) explains that the use of electronic money or e-money such as e-wallet and mobile banking can lead to waste or consumptive behavior because when making online shopping payment transactions, psychologically Generation Z does not feel physically spending money which can lead to dependence on making purchases online. Wasteful shopping behavior followed by a lack of understanding of financial products and risks is a financial problem that can be experienced by anyone, including generation z (Anggarini et al., 2021), which is why financial literacy is one of the basic skills that every individual must have to avoid problems. finances such as online shopping consumptive behavior, especially generation z who lives in the digital era where various things can be accessed easily through technology and internet networks.

LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Financial Literacy

Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 76/POJK.07/2016 defines financial literacy as behavior and attitudes influenced by knowledge, skills, and beliefs with the aim of improving financial management and decision-making profitably.

b. Financial Technology Digital Payment

According to the Financial Services Authority (OJK), Financial technology (Fintech) Digital Payment system is a category of fintech that provides much more practical, efficient and economical payment transaction services for all bills via mobile applications on smart phones (smartphones). The Financial Services Authority (OJK) further explained the meaning of fintech Digital Payment in the publication of the 2021-2025 Indonesian National Financial Literacy Strategy (SNLKI) as a digital financial service system that provides cashless payment services or without using cash (Financial Services Authority, 2019).

c. Financial

According to the definition of financial in the English dictionary Cambridge Dictionary and Merriam Webster, finance is defined as something related to money or finances, or how money is managed. This understanding is also supported by the definition of finance in the KBBI (Big Indonesian Dictionary), namely "concerning financial (affairs)". In this research, the definition of finance used is an individual's financial condition as seen from the level of income and

expenditure, including how their financial condition can meet all aspects of that person's needs (Shaid, 2022). Individual finances include how individuals spend their budget to meet their living needs.

d. Consumptive behaviour

Consumptive behavior is a pattern of individual consumption behavior that makes purchases not based on needs but rather desires caused by trends that are followed or the visual attractiveness of a product (Sustiyo, 2020). Kurniawan (2017) defines consumptive behavior as excessive behavior without using a priority scale or prioritizing desires and pleasures over needs in consuming something. The definition of consumer behavior is also defined as a type of consumption behavior that is carried out suddenly or without planning, arises from irrational attitudes (Effendi et al., 2021), and only prioritizes desires alone (Fattah et al., 2018).

e. State of The Art

Ayuningtyas & Irawan's (2021) study examined the influence of financial skills on the impulse buying actions of Gen Z buyers in Bandung with self-control as a mediator. This research involves the generation Z population born between 1997 and 2004. They live in Bandung. The total sample of 400 respondents was obtained through simple and purposive sampling techniques. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyzes were used.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research was carried out at 3 (three) state campuses, namely Cenderawasih University, Fattahul Muluk Papua State Islamic Institute (IAIN), and Jayapura Ministry of Health Health Polytechnic. This research targets generation Z students, who were born between 1997 and 2012. They are undergraduate students at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Cenderawasih University. Screening questions are used to determine the size of the research population to ensure that the respondents truly meet the established research criteria. The screening questions used can be seen in the following table:

Table 2.1: Screening Questions *circle one answer (Yes/No)

1	Have you ever made online purchase transactions through marketplaces (Tokopedia/ Shopee/ Lazada/ Bukalapak/ Blibli.com/others) or social media (Facebook/ Instagram/ Tiktok/ Whatsapp/ others) or certain online shop brand sites (Zalora/ Sorabel/ BendoStore/others) ?	Yes (go to next question)
		No (please stop, thank you for participating)
2	Have you made online purchase transactions (at least 3 times in the last 3 months) via marketplace (Tokopedia/ Shopee/ Lazada/ Bukalapak/ Blibli.com/others) or social media (Facebook/ Instagram/ Tiktok/ Whatsapp/ others) or websites? certain online shop brands (Zalora/ Sorabel/ BendoStore/ others)?	Yes (go to next question)
		No (please stop, thank you for participating)
3	Have you ever made an online shopping payment transaction or online shopping using a digital wallet application (e-wallet) such as Gopay/Ovo/Dana/LinkAja/ShoppePay or a mobile banking application such as Mobile Banking/ muamalat mobile/ Bank Papua?	Yes (go to next question)
		No (please stop, thank you for participating)
If the respondent answers "Yes" to all screening questions, then the respondent can fill out the next section of the questionnaire.		

All respondents who met the screening question criteria were considered as the sample for this study. In this research, total sampling techniques and non-probability sampling methods were used. According to Saat and Mania (2020:76), the non-probability sampling method, also known as saturated sampling or census, does not give every part of the population the same opportunity to be sampled. If the research is intended for generalization with a very small error rate or a relatively small population, such as less than 30 people, this method can be used (Sugiyono 2013:85). The minimum sample size for quantitative research is thirty samples, according to Karlinger and Lee (2000). The results of the classical assumption test in this research are described as follows:

a. Normality test

This is part of the classical assumption test which tests the distribution or distribution of the data to be analyzed to determine whether the data is normal or not for use in parametric analysis (Digdowisesiso, 2017) .

Figure 1: Histogram Curve

Figure 2: Normal P-P Plot Graph

Pada gambar kurva histogram tersebut terlihat bahwa bentuk kurva memuncak di bagian tengah dan melandai di kedua sisinya dengan nilai yang setara atau

b. Heteroscedasticity Test

According to Ghozali (2011:139) in Raharjo (2019), research data that does not have symptoms of heteroscedasticity is characterized by:

- 1) There is no clear pattern, such as wavy, widening then narrowing in the scatterplot image; as well as
- 2) The dots spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis.

Figure 3: Scatterplot graph

c. Uji Multikolinieritas Multicollinearity Test

Ghozali (2011:107-108) in Raharjo (2019) also states that data that does not experience symptoms of multicollinearity is proven by a Tolerance value that is greater than 0.100 (Tolerance >0.100) and a VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value that is smaller than 10 .00 (VIF < 10.00).

Table 2.2: Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients ^a			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
	Financial Literacy	.696	1.436
	Fintech DigiPayment	.366	2.735
	Financial	.321	3.115

d. Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 2.3: Multiple Regression Test Results

Model		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	1.505	2.446		.615	.542
	Financial Literacy	.174	.080	.157	2.181	.035
	Fintech_DigiPayment	.485	.082	.589	5.929	.000
	Financial	.307	.115	.284	2.674	.011

e. Hypothesis test

1) t test (partial test)

Formula for finding the value (df1; df2) t table (Raharjo, 2019): $(\alpha/2; n-k)$, where

$\alpha = 0.05$ (95% confidence level)

n = number of samples

k = number of research variables

2) F Test (Simultaneous Test)

Table 2.4: F Test Results (Simultaneous)

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	452.897	3	150.966	78.601	.000 ^b
Residual	78.747	41	1.921		
Total	531.644	44			

a. Dependent Variable: Consumptive_Behavior
b. Predictors: (Constant), Financial, Financial_Literacy, Fintech_DigiPayment

Formula to find the value (df1; df2) F table (quoted from Raharjo, 2019):

$(k; n-k-1)$, where

n = number of samples

k = number of independent variables

Thus, the value of (df1; df2) F table can be calculated:

$(3; 45-3-1) = (3; 41) = 2.83$

3) Coefficient of Determination

Table 2.5: Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.923 ^a	.852	.841	1.386

a. Predictors: (Constant), Financial, Financial_Literacy, Fintech_DigiPayment
b. Dependent Variable: Consumptive Behavior

The R Square (R²) value is 0.852, or almost 1, indicating that the independent variable is able to provide almost perfect information, namely the information needed to predict the dependent variable. In addition, the variables financial literacy, digital payment fintech, and finance accounted for 84.1% of consumer behavior variables, according to the Adjusted R Square value of 0.841. Meanwhile additional variables not discussed in this study influenced 15.9%.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. The Influence of Financial Literacy on the Consumptive Behavior of Generation Z in Jayapura City.

This indicator has an average value of respondents' answers of 4.07, which means that the average student "agrees" that at the beginning of every month they separate their money for each expense item, including the budget for entertainment such as online shopping, so it can be said that students' consumptive behavior is directly proportional to the decision on the amount of expenditure budget made by the individual each month. The greater the amount of spending budget made for entertainment such as online shopping, the higher the consumer behavior will be. Purwanto (2019) in his research also stated that the savings indicator in the financial literacy variable is the indicator that has the highest average value in encouraging student consumptive behavior, which means that the higher the amount of student savings, the higher the consumptive behavior. The results of this research contradict the findings of several previous studies, such as Ayuningtyas & Irawan (2021), Sustiyo (2020), and Kumalasari & Soesilo (2019), which found that generation Z (student) consumer behavior variables were negatively and significantly influenced by financial literacy.

b. The Influence of Fintech Digital Payment on the Consumer Behavior of Generation Z in Jayapura City.

The research results are supported by an average respondent answer of 3.98 on the digital payment fintech variable statement item (close to 4.00), which means that the average respondent "agrees" with each fintech digital payment variable statement item. On the perceived usefulness indicator, the average respondent's answer was 4.04, which shows that they "agree", the e-wallet application and mobile banking application have the features they need in the online shopping transaction process. This can increase the effectiveness of transactions and make them easier and more practical. The same thing is also shown in the perceived ease of use indicator. The average value of respondents' answers of 4.09 on this indicator also shows that respondents "agree", the e-wallet application and mobile banking application have features that are clear and easy to understand, making it possible for users to be able to access these services at any time. anytime and anywhere and control every transaction history made through their e-wallet account and mobile banking account. Not only that, respondents also have confidence in the security system of the e-wallet application and mobile banking application they use. They believe that personal data and every transaction that occurs in the e-wallet application and mobile banking application is stored and guaranteed safely. This statement is shown by the average respondent's answer to the security indicator of 3.71.

c. Financial Influence on the Consumer Behavior of Generation Z, Jayapura City.

According to the results of partial hypothesis testing, this study came to the same conclusion as the previous study: financial variables represented by student income and expenditure indicators have a positive and significant effect on consumer behavior. In the regression equation model, there is a coefficient value of the financial variable of 0.307, which indicates that every 1 unit increase in the financial variable will be followed by an increase of 0.307 in the consumer behavior variable. The average value of respondents' answers to the financial variable is 3.86, almost 4.00, indicating that most respondents agree with the details of the financial variable statement.

d. The Simultaneous Influence of Financial Literacy, Fintech Digital Payment, and Finance on Generation Z's Consumptive Behavior

Based on the results of simultaneous hypothesis testing (f test), it is proven that the consumer behavior of Gen Z, Papuan students in Jayapura City, State University, is positively and significantly influenced by financial knowledge, digital payment fintech, and finance simultaneously or separately. The R Square coefficient (R²) value is 0.852, or almost 1, indicating that the independent variable can provide almost perfect information for predicting the dependent variable. In other words, if students' financial literacy, use of digital payment fintech, and their financial level increase, their consumptive behavior will increase. In addition, the variables financial literacy, digital payment fintech, and finance accounted for 84.1% of consumer behavior variables, according to the Adjusted R Square value of 0.841.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the previous discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- a. Financial literacy is a factor that has a positive and significant impact on the consumer behavior of Generation Z, consisting of native Papuan students at the State University of Jayapura City. This shows that if students have extensive knowledge about finance, especially the amount of budget for each expenditure item set aside at the beginning of each month, including a budget for entertainment such as online shopping, and the ability to set aside their savings, they will be more likely to behave consumptively when shopping online.
- b. Papuan Native Students at Jayapura City State University see a positive and significant impact of digital payment financial technology, such as mobile banking and e-wallet products. This shows that students' perceptions of the usefulness, ease of use, and security of digital wallet (e-wallet) and mobile banking applications as online payment methods can influence their consumer behavior when shopping online.
- c. This shows that the higher the level of income and expenditure of students, the more students will shop online. Consumer behavior of Papuan students at the State University of Jayapura City is positively and significantly influenced by financial literacy, digital payment fintech, and finance variables simultaneously. This shows that if one of the three variables increases in a student, the student's consumer behavior will also increase.

Based on the findings in this research, the following suggestions can be concluded:

- a) Generation z, Indigenous Papuan students at Jayapura City State Universities are expected not to get used to the YOLO (You Only Live Once) and FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) mindset so as not to fall into excessive consumerist behavior which can endanger welfare finances in the future.
- b) Generation z, Indigenous Papuan students at Jayapura City State Universities are also expected to be wiser by having self-control in using digital payment financial technology (fintech digital payment) so that they are not easily tempted by the ease of transactions which if not controlled can encourage someone to consumer behavior.
- c) Generation z, Indigenous Papuan students at Jayapura City State Universities are also expected to be wiser in managing their personal income and expenses, so that the amount of money that can be saved can be used for long-term goals in the future, and not just for short-term goals. such as buying the desired online shop product.
- d) Researchers who in the future will conduct studies on the consumer behavior of Generation Z can develop financial literacy variable statement items to be more specific, especially regarding personal financial management, and can include other additional variables such as self-control and lifestyle. Researchers can also enlarge the scale of research subjects, such as taking students in the next generation or including development economics majors and accounting majors.

References

- 1) Abu Daqar, M. A. M., Arqawi, S., & Karsh, S. A. (2020). *Fintech in the eyes of millennials and generation z (the financial behavior and fintech perception)*. *Banks and Bank Systems*, 15(3), 20–28. [https://doi.org/10.21511/bbs.15\(3\).2020.03](https://doi.org/10.21511/bbs.15(3).2020.03)
- 2) Anggarini, D. R., Putri, A. D., & Lina, L. F. (2021). Literasi keuangan untuk generasi z di MAN 1 Pesawaran. *Jurnal Abdi Masyarakat Indonesia*, 1(1), 147–152. <https://doi.org/10.54082/jamsi.42>
- 3) Anjani, P. S., & Astiti, D. P. (2020). Hubungan kontrol diri dan konformitas terhadap perilaku konsumtif remaja penggemar animasi Jepang (anime) di Denpasar. *Jurnal Psikologi Udayana*, 144–155.
- 4) Annur, C.M. (2022). *Aplikasi mobile banking terpopuler di Indonesia, siapa juaranya?*. databoks.katadata.co.id
- 5) APJII, Asosiasi Penyelenggara Jasa Internet Indonesia. (2020). *Laporan Survei Internet APJII: 2019-2020 (Q2)*.
- 6) Artajasa, PT. (2022). *Mobile banking, gaya hidup baru kaum milenial dan gen z*. atmbersama.com.
- 7) Atkinson, A., & Messy, F.-A. (2012). *Measuring financial literacy: results of the OECD / International Network on Financial Education (INFE) pilot study*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5k9csfs90fr4-en>
- 8) Aulia, S. (2020). Pola perilaku konsumen digital dalam memanfaatkan aplikasi dompet digital. *Jurnal Komunikasi*, 12(2), 311. <https://doi.org/10.24912/jk.v12i2.9829>
- 9) Ayuningtyas, M. F., & Irawan, A. (2021). *The influence of financial literacy on Bandung generation z consumers impulsive buying behavior with self-control as mediating variable*. *Advanced International Journal of Business, Entrepreneurship and SMEs*, 3(9), 155–171. <https://doi.org/10.35631/aijbes.39012>
- 10) Azizah, L. N. (2021). *Literasi finansial*. Gramedia.Com.

- 11) Bank Indonesia. (2020a). *Fungsi utama/ kanal dan layanan/ QRIS/ dompet elektronik*. bi.go.id.
- 12) Bank Indonesia. (2020b). *Fungsi utama/ sistem pembayaran/ ritel/ elektronifikasi*. bi.go.id.
- 13) Bank Indonesia, & Departemen Komunikasi. (2018, December 1). *Mengenal financial technology*. bi.go.id.
- 14) Barlian, E. (2016). *Metodologi penelitian kualitatif dan kuantitatif*.
- 15) Binus University.ac.id.(2022). *Distribusi Normal*. Diakses pada 07 Juni 2022, dari <https://binus.ac.id/malang/2022/04/distribusi-normal/>
- 16) Boby. (2021). *Apa itu mbanking? Ini penjelasan, fungsi, dan cara kerjanya*. lifepal.co.id
- 17) BPS, Badan Pusat Statistik. (2021a). *Berita resmi statistik: hasil sensus penduduk 2020*.
- 18) BPS, Badan Pusat Statistik. (2021b). *Statistik e-commerce 2021*.
- 19) Carissa, A. F. (2021). Pengaruh literasi keuangan dan gaya hidup terhadap perilaku konsumtif mahasiswa (studi kasus mahasiswa jurusan manajemen fakultas ekonomi dan bisnis Universitas Muhammadiyah Sumatera Utara).
- 20) Charness, N., & Boot, W. R. (2016). *Technology, gaming, and social networking in handbook of the psychology of aging (eight edition)*. Sciencedirect.Com.
- 21) CIMB NIAGA DSRResearch. (2020). *Fintech report 2020: maintaining growth during pandemic*.
- 22) Davis, F. D. (1989). *Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology*. *MIS Quarterly: Management Information Systems*, 13(3), 319–339. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- 23) Dewi, L. G. K., Herawati, N. T., & Adiputra, I. M. P. (2021). Penggunaan e-money terhadap perilaku konsumtif mahasiswa yang dimediasi kontrol diri. *Ekuitas (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan)*, 5(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.24034/j25485024.y2021.v5.i1.4669>
- 24) Digdownwiseiso, K. (2017). *Metodologi penelitian ekonomi dan bisnis*.
- 25) Effendi, U., Rahmayanti, R., Usman, R. F., Abubakar, & MR, M. (2021). *Characteristics of consumptive behavior in online shop: shopping trends during the covid-19 pandemic*. *Jurnal Sosiohumaniora Kodepena Information Center for Indonesian Social Sciences*, Vol.2,No.1. <http://jsk.kodepena.org/index.php/jsk>
- 26) Fattah, F. A., Indriayu, M., & Sunarto. (2018). Pengaruh literasi keuangan dan pengendalian diri terhadap perilaku konsumtif siswa SMA Muhammadiyah 1 Karanganyar. *BISE: Jurnal Pendidikan Bisnis Dan Ekonomi*, Vol.4, No.1.
- 27) Ghozali, I. (2011). *Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 19*. Semarang. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- 28) Ghozali, I. (2016). *Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 26*. Semarang (2018). Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro. ISBN: 979-704-015-1.
- 29) Gunawan, A. A. & Sunardi, HP. (2016). Pengaruh kompensasi dan disiplin kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan pada PT Gesit Nusa Tangguh. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis*, Vol.16, No.1.
- 30) Hadad, M. D., & Dewan Komisioner-OJK, K. (2017). *Financial technology (Fintech) di Indonesia*.
- 31) Hamdani, M. (2018). Analisis tingkat literasi keuangan dan pengaruhnya terhadap perilaku keuangan pada mahasiswa prodi Manajemen Universitas Terbuka. *Jurnal Bakti Masyarakat Indonesia*, Vol.1, No.1, 139–145. cnnindonesia.com,
- 32) Harahap, N., & Lubis, S. D. (2019). *Metodologi penelitian kuantitatif*.

- 33) Harjayanti, D. R., Rovita, A., & Yuwono, T. (2020). Pengaruh tingkat Pendidikan, tingkat literasi keuangan, instrumen literasi Keuangan pada keputusan pembelian pada media *online* (Studi kasus masyarakat di daerah Tangerang selatan). *Jurnal Mandiri: Ilmu Pengetahuan, Seni, Dan Teknologi*, 4(2), 199–209. <https://doi.org/10.33753/mandiri.v4i2.127>
- 34) Haryanto, L., & Rosyid, F. (1997). Perilaku konsumtif berdasar locus of control pada remaja putri.
- 35) Hermawan, S., & Amirullah. (2016). *Metode penelitian bisnis pendekatan kuantitatif & kualitatif*.
- 36) Indrajit, R. E. (2002). *Electronic commerce: strategi dan konsep bisnis di dunia maya*.
- 37) Indrianawati, E., & Soesatyo, Y. (2015). Pengaruh tingkat pendapatan dan pengetahuan ekonomi terhadap tingkat konsumsi mahasiswa program pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Surabaya. *Jurnal Ekonomi Pendidikan Dan Kewirausahaan*.
- 38) Insana, D. R. M., & Johan, R. S. (2020). Analisis pengaruh penggunaan uang elektronik terhadap perilaku konsumtif mahasiswa pendidikan ekonomi Universitas Indraprasta PGRI. *Journal of Applied Business and Economics (JABE)*, Vol.7, No.2, 209–224.
- 39) IPSOS media conference. (2020). *Evolusi industri dompet digital: strategi menang tanpa bakar uang*.
- 40) Junaidi. (2010). *Titik persentase distribusi f*. Diakses pada 07 Juni 2022, dari <https://junaidichaniago.wordpress.com>
- 41) Kadence International, PT. (2021). *Digital payment and financial services usage and behavior in Indonesia*.
- 42) Katadata Insight Center, & Kredivo. (2021). *Perilaku konsumen e-commerce Indonesia*.
- 43) Kemendikbud, Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan. (2017). *Buku materi pendukung literasi finansial: Gerakan Literasi Nasional (GLN)*. kemendikbud.go.id.
- 44) Kominfo, Kementerian Komunikasi dan Informatika. (2019). *Perkembangan ekonomi digital di Indonesia*.
- 45) Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2009). *Philip Kotler dan Kevin Lane Keller: Manajemen pemasaran (edisi ketiga belas, jilid satu)* (A. Maulana & W. Hardani (eds.); Tiga Belas). Pearson Education, Inc. Diterjemahkan oleh: Penerbit Erlangga dan dicetak oleh: PT. Gelora Aksara Pratama.
- 46) Kumala, I., & Mutia, I. (2020). Pemanfaatan Aplikasi Dompet Digital Terhadap Transaksi Retail Mahasiswa. *Seminar Nasional Riset Dan Teknologi (SEMNAS RISTEK) 2020*.
- 47) Kumalasari, D., & Soesilo, Y. H. (2019). Pengaruh literasi keuangan, modernitas individu, uang saku dan kontrol diri terhadap perilaku konsumtif mahasiswa prodi S1 pendidikan ekonomi angkatan tahun 2016 Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Negeri Malang. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.17977/UM014v12i12019p061>
- 48) Kurniawan, C. (2017). Analisis faktor-faktor yang mempengaruhi perilaku konsumtif ekonomi pada mahasiswa.
- 49) Kusuma, V. T. (2020). Pengaruh dompet elektronik terhadap perilaku konsumtif bagi mahasiswa di Universitas Raharja. *Jurnal Ilmiah Sekolah Tinggi Teknologi Informasi NIIT*, 16(2). kominfo.go.id
- 50) Lestari, C. D. (2021). Pengaruh literasi keuangan, sosiodemografi, finansial, dan pandemi covid-19 terhadap keputusan keuangan dalam penggunaan e-wallet pada generasi z (Studi kasus: mahasiswa S1 di Jabodetabek).
- 51) McDermott, K. (2017). *Future trends in consumer behavior*.
- 52) Meiryani. (2021). *Memahami uji normalitas dalam model regresi*. Diakses pada 07 Juni 2022, dari <https://accounting.binus.ac.id/2021/08/06/memahami-uji-normalitas-dalam-model-regresi/>
- 53) Miysell, K dan Wasisto, J. (2020). Persepsi mahasiswa program studi ilmu perpustakaan Universitas Diponegoro pada peluang kerja *information professional*. *Jurnal Ilmu Perpustakaan*, Vol.9, No.2.

- 54) Mufirdah, D. (2020). Pengaruh *convenience*, *performance*, dan *privacy* dalam penerapan aplikasi *mobile banking* terhadap perilaku konsumtif remaja dalam berbelanja *online*.
- 55) Mujahidin, A., & Astuti, R. P. F. (2020). Pengaruh *fintech e-wallet* terhadap perilaku konsumtif pada generasi milenial. *INOVIZ: Jurnal Inovasi Dan Bisnis* 8.
- 56) Nawawi, H. H. (2020). Penggunaan *e-wallet* di kalangan mahasiswa. *Jurnal Emik*, 3(2). <https://qwords.com/blog/sejarah-singkat-internet/>,
- 57) Nirmala, Miftah, M., & Murtatik, S. (2020). Analisis gaya hidup dan literasi keuangan terhadap perilaku mahasiswa dalam *cashless society*. *KORELASI (Konferensi Riset Nasional Ekonomi, Manajemen, Dan Akuntansi)*.
- 58) Nur'Aini, S., Wahyudi, & Siswantini, T. (2021). Analisis perilaku keuangan generasi z pada mahasiswa UPN Veteran Jakarta di masa pandemi. *Jurnal Riset Bisnis*, Vol.5, No.1.
- 59) Nur Fauzi, I. S & Sulistyowati (2022). Literasi keuangan dan perilaku keuangan berpengaruh terhadap perilaku konsumtif pada *player call of duty: mobile*. *Jurnal Kajian Ilmiah*, Vol.22, No.2.
- 60) OECD. (2018). *OECD/INFE toolkit for measuring financial literacy and financial inclusion*.
- 61) OECD, *Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development*. (2014). *PISA 2012 results: students and money (Volume VI)* (PISA). OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264208094-en>
- 62) OJK, Otoritas Jasa Keuangan. (2016). *Salinan peraturan Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Nomor 76/POJK.07/2016*.
- 63) OJK, Otoritas Jasa Keuangan. (2021). *Strategi nasional literasi keuangan Indonesia 2021-2025*.
- 64) Otoritas Jasa Keuangan. (2017). *Literasi keuangan/OJK 2013*. ojk.go.id.
- 65) Otoritas Jasa Keuangan. (2019). *Yuk mengenal fintech! Keuangan digital yang tengah naik daun*. sikapiuangmu.ojk.go.id.
- 66) Purnawijaya, F. M (2019). Pengaruh disiplin kerja dan fasilitas kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan pada Kedai 27 di Surabaya. *AGORA*, Vol.7, No.1.
- 67) Purwanto, E. (2019). Buku monograf: analisis literasi keuangan, faktor demografi dan pendapatan terhadap perilaku konsumtif mahasiswa (1st ed.). *Sasanti Institute*.
- 68) Raharjo, S. (2019). *Trik analisis regresi linear berganda sekaligus uji asumsi klasik dengan SPSS*. Youtube
- 69) Ramadanti, H. R. A., Nawir, J., & Marlina. (2021). Analisis perilaku keuangan generasi z pada *cashless society (analysis of financial behavior of generation z on cashless society)*. *Jurnal Visionida*, 7(2).
- 70) Ramadhan, B. (2020). *Pengguna dompet digital di Indonesia mulai tidak terpengaruh promo*. teknioia.com.
- 71) Repository Universitas Ciputra. *BAB III metode penelitian-Dspace@UC*. Diakses pada 08 Juni 2022, dari <https://dSPACE.UC.AC.ID/>
- 72) Repository Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara. *BAB II LANDASAN TEORI*. Diakses pada 15 Juni 2022, dari <http://repository.uinsu.ac.id/4932/4/BAB%20II.pdf>
- 73) Riadi, M. (2018, June 9). *Pengertian, aspek dan karakteristik perilaku konsumtif*. kajianpustaka.com.
- 74) Saat, S., & Mania, S. (2020). *Pengantar metodologi penelitian: panduan bagi peneliti pemula*.
- 75) Santoso, G., & Triwijayati, A. (2018). Gaya pengambilan keputusan pembelian pakaian secara *online* pada generasi z Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmu Keluarga dan Konsumen*, 11(3), 231-242. <https://doi.org/10.24156/jikk.2018.11.3.231>
- 76) SEA e-Conomy, R. (2021). *e-Conomy SEA 2021: Roaring 20s "The SEA digital decade."*
- 77) Shaid, N. J. (2022, March 4). *Apa itu finansial: definisi, jenis, fungsi, dan tujuannya*. kompas.com.
- 78) Sharma Nariyanuri, S. (2021). *Southeast Asia e-money market report*.

- 79) Silalahi, R. Y. B. (2020). Pengaruh literasi keuangan dan gaya hidup terhadap perilaku konsumtif berbelanja *Online. Khazanah Ilmu Berazam*, Vol.3, No.2.
- 80) Simangunsong, E. (2018). *Generation z buying behaviour in Indonesia: opportunities for retail businesses. Mix: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen*, 8(2), 243. <https://doi.org/10.22441/mix.2018.v8i2.004>
- 81) Simangunsong, R. M. S., Brahmana, K. M. B., & Simarmata, N. I. P. (2021). Pengaruh harga diri dan kelompok teman sebaya terhadap perilaku konsumtif pada mahasiswa generasi z. *Jurnal Psychomutiara*, 4, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.51544/psikologi.v4i2.2541>
- 82) Sircolo. (2021). *Navigating Indonesia's e-commerce: omnichannel as the future of retail*.
- 83) Stawati, V. (2020). Pengaruh profitabilitas, leverage, dan ukuran perusahaan terhadap penghindaran pajak. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Bisnis: Jurnal Program Studi Akuntansi*, 6(2). ISSN (print): 2443-3071, ISSN (online): 2503-0337.
- 84) Sugiyono. (2013). *Metode penelitian kuantitatif kualitatif dan R&D*.
- 85) Susanti, A., & Rikah. (2020). Penggunaan media sosial instagram dan literasi keuangan terhadap perilaku konsumtif berbelanja *online* generasi milenial. *JAB*, Vol.6 No.01.
- 86) Susanti, Hardini, H. T., & Bahtiar, M. D. (2020). *The effect of financial literacy, financial technology, and digital promotion on online purchasing decisions in the covid-19 pandemic era*.
- 87) Sustiyo, J. (2020). Apakah literasi keuangan mempengaruhi perilaku konsumsi generasi z? *Jurnal Manajemen Mandiri Saburai*, 04(01).
- 88) Sutriati, Kartikowati, S., & Riadi, R. (2018). Pengaruh pendapatan dan gaya hidup terhadap perilaku konsumtif pada mahasiswa jurusan Pendidikan Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial FKIP Universitas Riau. *JOM FKIP VOLUME*, 5.
- 89) Syafnidawati. (2020, November 8). *Data sekunder*. raharja.ac.id
- 90) Syifa, L. (2019). Pengaruh kemudahan penggunaan *mobile banking* terhadap perilaku konsumtif mahasiswa FITK UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta.
- 91) Thohiroh, A. Q. (2015). Perilaku konsumtif melalui online shopping.
- 92) Tuhumena, R. (2020, May 22). *Tutorial SPSS: Uji asumsi klasik dengan SPSS*. Youtube.
- 93) Venia, M., Marzuki, F., & Yuliniar. (2021). Analisis faktor yang mempengaruhi perilaku impulse buying (Studi kasus pada generasi z pengguna e-commerce). 2, 929–941.
- 94) Widiasmara, H. (2021, January 24). *Pentingnya keamanan digital di era revolusi industri 4.0*. kumparan.com.
- 95) Widyawati, R. (2018). Analisis kualitas layanan pembayaran mahasiswa di Bank Muamalat kantor kas Universitas Amikom Yogyakarta. *Jurnal Pro Bisnis*, Vol.11, No.1. ISSN: 1979-9258, e-ISSN: 2442-4536
- 96) Wikielektronika.com (2022). *Tabel t statistika*. Diakses pada 08 Juni 2022, dari <https://wikielektronika.com/tabel-t-statistika/>
- 97) Yaniawati, R. P. (2020, April 14). *Penelitian studi kepustakaan (library research)*.
- 98) Yudha, K. B. K. (2019, March 8). *Jangan salah! Ini perbedaan e-money dan e-wallet dalam mempermudah transaksi*. finansialku.com.
- 99) Yuliara, I. M. (2016). *Modul regresi linier berganda*.
- 100) Yushita, A. N. (2017). Pentingnya literasi keuangan bagi pengelolaan keuangan pribadi. *Jurnal Nominal*.